

Your hernia operation

Is it correct that you were operated on for a hernia in one groin when you were between 10 and 19 years old?

Yes

No

Please explain why you answered "No":

Is it correct that you were only operated on once in the groin that was operated on when you were between 10 and 19 years old (i.e., you have not been operated on multiple times in the same groin)?

Yes

No

Please explain why you answered "No":

Do you suspect that the hernia has returned after your operation?

Yes

No

If "Yes", has it been confirmed by someone other than yourself that the hernia has returned?

No

Yes, by a doctor

Other

Please explain why you answered "Other":
